

10th Annual Spring Scientific Symposium in Anaesthesiology and Intensive Care

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PROCEEDING

European Society of
Anaesthesiology and
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Symposium in Anaesthesiology and Intensive Care

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IN ANAESTHESIOLOGY AND INTENSIVE CARE**

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SPECIFICITY OF NEONATAL ANESTHESIA

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Neonates and premature babies belong to the category of a high-risk group of patients for anesthesia. Neonatal anesthesia is distinguished by a number of specificities, starting from anatomical characteristics (difficult intubation, ventilation, and intravenous route), hemodynamic stability of these patients and fluid management, to the pharmacological peculiarities of this group of patients and their response to administered drugs, which can leave long-term consequences.

Neonates are distinguished by many specific differences, first and foremost the respiratory system. Starting from the anatomical dead space differences of infants (early infancy > 3 ml/kg vs. adults 2.2 ml/kg) in relation to their larger head size is much greater compared with adults; furthermore, the epiglottis of neonates is narrower, larger, and in a superior position compared with adults. Infants are obligate nasal breathers due to the low airway resistance through their nasal passage. The upper respiratory tract of neonates is compliant so dynamic collapse is more common. The breathing of infants is more severely impacted when their relatively smaller airway diameters are narrowed by secretions in the endotracheal tube.

Reduced elastic recoil of lungs and high closing volume makes it difficult to maintain the functional residual capacity (FRC) of neonates. Infants have the following properties to increase and maintain FRC: First, the post-inspiratory activity of the intercostal and diaphragmatic muscles (self-recruitment maneuver); second, high respiratory rates with short expiratory times (auto-positive end-expiratory pressure (PEEP) or dynamic hyperinflation); and lastly, laryngeal adduction in expiration to increase expiratory airway resistance (functional PEEP).

The mechanical ventilation of neonatal patients is an uncertain practice because small changes in tidal volume can induce unintentional hyperventilation or hypoventilation, leading to lung injury. Traditional mechanical ventilators of the anesthetic field were unable to deliver small tidal volumes (20 ml for most ventilators), so most pediatric anesthesiologists prefer pressure-controlled ventilation. Nowadays it is possible to apply low tidal volumes, thereby avoiding volutrauma and atelectrauma. These volume-targeted modes of ventilation can reduce the potential for ventilator-induced lung injury. One group of authors recommends mild hypercapnia (PaCO₂ 45–55 mmHg) as a „respira-

tory care strategy” that is used to reduce the potential for lung injury. In preterm infants at risk of intraventricular hemorrhage of the brain, both hypocapnia (PaCO₂ < 39 mmHg) and hypercapnia (PaCO₂ > 60 mmHg) as well as magnitude fluctuations in PaCO₂ should be avoided.

Optimal oxygen saturation target - excess oxygen can be harmful to neonates, as it can result in conditions such as retinopathy of prematurity (ROP), bronchopulmonary dysplasia (BPD), injury to the developing brain, and DNA damage that can lead to childhood cancer; however, in a recent meta-analysis, no significant differences in mortality, BPD, ROP, and neurodevelopmental outcomes were found between restricted (SpO₂ 85 to 89%) and liberal (SpO₂ 91 to 95%) oxygen group. The optimal level of oxygen guidelines to reduce the risk of ROP while also improving the outcome and development of preterm infants is still unclear. A recent review suggests that wider and intermediate SpO₂ targets, such as 87–94% or 88–94%, are safe for vulnerable patients, and it also an optimal saturation during anesthesia as well as postoperatively.

Cardiovascular system, in addition to the anatomical differences, the first place is the transition from fetal to adult circulation. A very important task during anesthesia is to maintain hemodynamic stability, especially when it comes to urgent operations and hemodynamically unstable patients due to an underlying disease. Also, it is important to think about the circulation, which is dynamic and can change into fetal circulation at any moment. It is important to maintain blood pressure, but in the literature, there are many dilemmas when defining hypotension, especially in preterm infants with low GA. We know that after birth, the pressure gradually increases in newborns. The latest works that were done on a large number of patients, however, suggested that the most important parameter for BP is actually MAP, and that regardless of GA, and mean arterial pressure below 30mmHg should be defined as hypotension (for babies under 1kg and under 28 weeks, the limit is 25mmHg) and treat it in a timely manner, especially during anesthesia. For the treatment of hypotension, the use of bolus doses of crystalloids is recommended, as well as the use of colloids. For colloids, human albumins have an advantage over the use of synthetic colloids, but also for albumins there is a limitation in the literature and they should be applied carefully.

Normal hemoglobin (Hb) levels of neonates are in the range of 140–200 g/l. Correction of anemia is the subject of scientific debates, mostly in full-term newborns hemoglobin is tolerated up to 90g/l and in premature infants up to 70g/l, depending on the general condition and comorbidities. The use of blood and blood derivatives is restrictive due to the negative effects of transfusion, but there is still a section of authors who give priority to oxygen capacity and advocate transfusion. Before the operation, anemia should be corrected and the target concentration of Hb during transfusion is 120-140g/l.

The coagulation system in full-term infants is generally preserved and does not require major corrections except for the administration of vitamin K, but premature infants have a tendency to bleed and any disorder should be corrected before surgery. The literature recommends that every thrombocytopenia below 100,000 should be taken seriously, and below 50,000 must be corrected. Not infrequently, in persistent bleeding, the use of recombinant coagulation factor 7 is recommended, and the use of tranexamic acid does not yet have sufficient scientific evidence in this category of patients.

Knowledge of pharmacology in these patients is extremely important, due to the unpredictable effects of drugs and the insufficient number of clinically confirmed studies, as well as imprecise recommendations sufficiently scientifically supported. Opioid addiction, hyperalgesia, and propofol-infusion syndrome are also known, but research is ongoing. During the treatment and anesthesia of these patients, we are forced to use "off-label" drugs, because only less than 5% have passed the clinical study, which is an insufficient number for a precise clinical pharmacology practice. Only three anesthetic drugs (remifentanyl, rocuronium, and sevoflurane) had updated labeling for neonates, but none included premature infants. Take care of the dosage of the drugs and the correct dilution so that we do not burden our small patients with excess volume. Insufficient knowledge of absorption, distribution, and clearance, then the immaturity of the liver, kidneys, hematoencephalic circulation, etc., points us to caution and to a careful application of anesthetics and other drugs.

The anesthesiologist scheduled to care for a newborn must have a reliable comprehensive system to assess the stability of patients and use this information in the development of their anesthetic plan of care. Important historical information that can be gathered from the medical record includes gestational age, weight, and birth events (including Apgar scores at 1, 5, and 10min). Finally, the anesthesiologist must closely inspect the care requirements of the neonate in the last 24h to ascertain the likely starting point for support in the operative suite. Physical examination of the infants is required to assess the stability and patency of the neonate's airway and gas exchange. If mechanical ventilator support is needed, close inspec-

tions of the placement of the airway on chest X-ray, current ventilator settings, and the result of the most recent blood gas are needed. The anesthesia provider must perform a careful assessment for signs or symptoms of cardiovascular abnormalities and stability. Hydration (volume) status should be assessed via vital signs (heart rate, blood pressure), capillary refill, and urine output. Any evidence of dehydration should be fully corrected before the induction of anesthesia except in true life-threatening emergent situations. Lastly, the anesthesiologist must assess the safety of the current vascular access and associated infusions and determine if the access will be sufficient for perioperative care. Common anesthesia practices in neonates include the routine use of physiologic monitors (ECG, non-invasive blood pressure, temperature, pulse oximetry, and end-tidal carbon dioxide). Care must be taken to preserve normal temperature during transport to and from the operative suites and to the heating of the operative environment. Continuous glucose delivery throughout the duration of the procedure is required with the potential to monitor intermittent serum glucose levels. General anesthesia with the placement of endotracheal tube is generally required for the safe care of the neonate. Anesthesia typically consists of a balanced combination of volatile agents supplemented with opioids for hemodynamic stability.

In recent years, the neurotoxicity of anesthetics, primarily inhalational anesthetics, has attracted a lot of attention from the professional public. A lot of studies on animal models have been done that confirm that early exposure to general anesthetics leads to apoptosis and programmed cell death, even to changes in the mitochondria themselves, which is reflected in changes in the behavior of these animals as well as in the lethal outcome. These studies were not only done on mice and rats, but there is also evidence on pigs and primates, which indicates how much anesthetics have a neurotoxic effect and affect neurobehavioral development. Long-term studies confirm that children who were repeatedly exposed to anesthesia in early childhood have learning difficulties, but the influence of the environment as well as earlier comorbidities cannot be excluded here - prematurity, sepsis, HIC, hydrocephalus, BPD, etc. Further research is needed.

Pain treatment perioperatively and post-operatively is very important. Earlier theories that babies do not feel pain have been rejected because it has been proven that nociceptors and pain receptors develop very early, already at 9 weeks GA, and gradually mature, therefore every procedure should be taken seriously and pain treated. Insufficient and inadequate pain treatment has long-term, consequences and plays a major role in the development of hyperalgesia, and leaves a mark on the neurobehavioral impact. In assessing pain evaluation of vital parameters, and behavioral parameters is useful. There are many scales for assessing pain, the most frequently used are the PIPP scale, and the FLACC scale.

In the pain treatment opioids are recommended, in first place fentanyl and morphine, which are also recommended for further analgosedation in the ICU. Scientific evidence on the potential neurotoxicity of opioids due to the peculiarities of cerebral circulation in babies has not been proven and it has been confirmed that the administration of both fentanyl and morphine does not lead to cell damage and can be safely administered to these patients. Remifentanyl is recommended for short-term sedation as well as for intubation and procedural pain management. Paracetamol, one of the most commonly used analgesics, can be safely administered at a dose of 7.5 mg/kg iv 4-6 times a day, and only long-term use of high doses can manifest a hepatotoxic effect. It is recommended to use it with opioids as part of multimodal analgesia.

In postoperative care, some newborns with apnea, neurological disease, or anemia should be identified and considered at high risk. These patients require 12-h post-operative monitoring. Healthy newborns can be monitored for 6 h post-operatively, with surgery scheduled early in the day and standard monitoring (ECG and pulse oximetry) in the post-anesthetic care unit.

Conclusion: Neonatal anesthesia is fraught with potential risk for the patient and stress for the anesthesiologist. Reducing the risk of neonatal anesthesia requires recognition of the risk factors, where possible preventing their occurrence, and being able to manage the consequences of the problem. Neonatal anesthesia is best provided by two anesthetists working together.

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